

chloride on diphenyl in presence of zinc dust isolated *p*-benzyldiphenyl as flat needles from hot glacial acetic and as plates from alcohol, m.p. 85° and *isobenzyldiphenyl* as monosymmetrical needles, m.p. 54°.

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A Short Note on the Chromium Biguanide Complexes.

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Complex compounds of biguanide with bivalent copper, cobalt and nickel have been described long ago (Ratbke, *Ber.*, 1878, **11**, 967; 1879, **12**, 777; Rackmann, *Annalen*, 1911, **376**, 163). The constitution of these compounds is, however, still under dispute. As these compounds are very sparingly soluble in water, the study of their constitution by usual physico-chemical methods is rendered thereby extremely difficult.

We have now, however, succeeded in preparing soluble biguanide complexes of trivalent chromium. The free complex base, which forms the mother substance and from which a series of salts is in the course of preparation, has been obtained as beautiful ruby-red crystals of the following composition: $[\text{Cr}(\text{C}_2\text{N}_5\text{H}_6)_3] \text{H.OH}$, the biguanide molecule acting as a bidentate group and occupying two co-ordinate positions. The compound is, therefore, expected to give rise to optically active enantiomers. The substance is strongly basic and in aqueous solution behaves as a tri-acidic base, as could be concluded from the freezing-point and conductivity data as well as from the titer-value of the base in aqueous solution.

Fuller details about the preparation, properties and constitution of the compound and its derivatives will be published in due course.

Similar compounds with trivalent cobalt atom have also been prepared and will form the subject matter of a separate paper.

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